

SUPERCONDUCTING STABILIZED X-BAND OSCILLATORS

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ABSTRACT

Two X - Band oscillators have been designed, built and tested using planar HTSC superconducting resonators for stabilization. The reaction type oscillator uses a YBaCuO HTSC ring resonator and the parallel feedback oscillator uses a thallium based HTSC half wavelength resonator with an unloaded $Q = 21000$. The design and development of these oscillators and characteristics of HTSC resonators will be discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Superconducting films of both $Y_1Ba_2Cu_3O_x$ (YBCO) and $Tl_2Ba_2Ca_1Cu_2O_y$ (TBCCO) were used for this work. The 123 films were grown at ETDL by laser ablation. The laser ablation system is typical [1] in that 248 nm light from a pulsed excimer laser is focused onto a bulk target of YBCO so that the ablated material is deposited onto a substrate positioned 7 cm from the target. In this particular case, the

substrate is a single crystal of MgO heated during deposition to a temperature of 720 C. The ambient atmosphere during deposition is 200 mTorr of oxygen and is raised to approximately one-half an atmosphere during the post-deposition cooling phase. The deposition rate is typically 550 nm/minute and the YBCO film used here was 800 nm thick.

The TBCCO films used for these experiments were also deposited by laser ablation but were obtained commercially from Superconductor Technologies, Inc. The deposition process for these films is somewhat similar to that previously described, although a post-deposition anneal in a thallium atmosphere is required. The substrate material for the TI-based film was single-crystal $LaAlO_3$. The two different substrate materials have considerably different dielectric constants. [1] [2] At 77 K, the dielectric constant for MgO is 9.6 at 10 GHz, but is 23.8 at 6.2 GHz for $LaAlO_3$. The loss tangent is about 6×10^{-5} for both materials. Thallium based films have transition temperatures of approximately 110K, while YBaCuO films transition at

approximately 90K.

A resonator was patterned in each of the HTSC films previously described to stabilize two X -band oscillators. A ring resonator was patterned in a YBaCuO HTSC film and a half wavelength resonator was patterned in the thalium based HTSC film. The signal is capacitively coupled in and out of the resonators, (see figure 1).

Figure 1.

The unloaded Q of the thalium based resonator and the YBaCuO resonator are 21,000 and 1,200 respectively, measured with approximately -25dBm at the resonator. The unloaded Q's of the resonators are calculated from their loaded Q's and their insertion losses at resonance. [3], [4] The high Q of the thalium HTSC ring is attributable to a very high quality HTSC film and also having an HTSC ground plane, whereas the YBaCuO resonator has a silver ground plane. It is believed that a double sided HTSC substrate can increase the Q of a resonator by an order of magnitude. Both of these HTSC resonators exhibit similar characteristics versus temperature. As temperature decreases the surface resistivity

of the HTSC decreases, resulting in a higher Q and thus a lower insertion loss for a constant amount of coupling in and out of the resonator. Actual measurements of insertion loss and Q versus temperature for the double sided Thalium resonator show that the insertion loss of the resonator decreases from 27dB at 93.6K to 15.6dB at 46.0K, (see figures 2, 3).

Figure 2.

Superconducting Technologies Inc.
 Double Sided HTS Resonator
 Substrate: Lanthanum Aluminate

Figure 3.

A second characteristic which changes as a function of temperature is the ring's resonant frequency. This is explained by the following relation. [5]

- 1) $f = v_{ph}/\lambda_c$
- 2) $v_{ph} = 1/(\mu_0 \epsilon_{ff})^{1/2} [1 + (2\lambda(T)/d) \coth(b/\lambda(T))]^{-1/2}$
- 3) $\lambda(T) = \lambda(0) [1 - (T/T_c)^4]^{-1/2}$

$\lambda(T)$ = Penetration Depth
 T = Resonator Temperature
 T_c = Transition Temperature of Superconducting Film
 f = resonant frequency
 v_{ph} = phase velocity

λ_c = wavelength
 ϵ_{ff} = effective dielectric
 b = film thickness
 d = substrate thickness

Measurements show that the thalium based HTSC resonator's frequency changes 20MHz as the ring's temperature decreases from 94K to 46 K, (see figure 4). The design and results of two X band oscillators using these superconducting resonators for stabilization are represented.

HTSC THALIUM BASED RESONATOR'S RESONANT FREQUENCY VS. TEMPERATURE

Figure 4.

SUPERCONDUCTING OSCILLATORS

REACTION TYPE OSCILLATOR

The reaction type oscillator is composed of two separate and different substrates, an

alumina substrate and a magnesium oxide (MgO) substrate (see Figure 5).

REACTION TYPE OSCILLATOR

Figure 5.

The alumina substrate is metallized with gold on both top and ground planes, and the MgO substrate is metallized with silver on the ground plane and with a YBaCuO superconducting film deposited on the other plane. Both substrates are soldered to a brass test fixture with a low temperature solder . The low temperature solder is precautionary and meant to reduce stress on the superconductor film. The active part of the oscillator is located on the alumina substrate. A NEC 73183 HEMT is attached to the gold microstrip pattern that includes DC bias circuitry and RF stubs designed to induce oscillation. The MgO substrate has a ring resonator and a 50 ohm line etched into its superconducting film. The 50 ohm superconducting line is soldered to the gold 50 ohm impedance line leading from the

HEMT's drain. The oscillator's output is soldered at the opposite end of the superconducting line. All superconductor soldering is done with an indium based solder manufactured by Supersolder Technologies Inc. The oscillator, when cooled below liquid nitrogen temperatures, locks to the superconducting ring resonator and oscillates at 9.33GHz.

This oscillator was designed on a linear microwave simulator using measured small signal s-parameters. [6], [7] A reaction type oscillator has its stabilizing resonator located at its output, in this case the drain. The simulator was used to design the required networks to induce a free running oscillation, (see figure 6).

SCHEMATIC OF REACTION TYPE OSCILLATOR

Figure 6.

[8] This small signal analysis is a rough approximation, since oscillators actually operate in a large signal, nonlinear mode. Also room temperature s- parameter data was used instead of cryogenic temperature data,

contributing to the inaccuracies in the predicted operating frequency. Provided the ring resonator has a high quality factor, predicting the exact free running oscillation frequency is unnecessary, the ring will lock the oscillator to its resonant frequency.

The ring resonator, designed to resonate at 9.3GHz, is separated from the 50 ohm line by five mils. In this configuration the ring resonator can be modelled as a parallel RLC circuit connected to the 50 ohm line through a transformer. At resonance, the real impedance at the ring's plane is very large and the rate of reactance change versus frequency near resonance is also very large. The ring resonator was placed $3/4 \lambda$ away from the drain of the transistor, so the high impedance is transformed to a low impedance at the transistor, while retaining a large reactance change versus frequency. Optimal placement for the ring is $1/4\lambda$ away from the drain, but the ring size made this placement physically unattainable. This transformation insures that the resistance seen by the drain of the transistor is smaller than the negative resistance seen looking into the drain of the transistor, a condition for oscillation. The simulation predicts a negative resistance approximately equal to -80 ohms. Assuming the superconducting ring has a loaded $Q = 600$, the drain sees approximately 20 ohms, therefore this condition for oscillation is met. The main purpose of the ring is to keep the oscillator locked at a specific frequency as the HEMT's characteristics change, due to a shift

in temperature, change in operating voltage, transistor aging, etc. Since the ring's reactance change versus frequency is large compared to the

HEMT's reactance change, the oscillator locks to the ring's resonant frequency.

The oscillator was tested using both a spectrum analyzer and a network analyzer. The oscillator was placed in a cryostat and its output connected to the spectrum analyzer. The cryostat was cooled to 39K, well below the superconductor's transition temperature. The HEMT was biased at a drain voltage of 2.0V (V_{ds}) and the gate was biased at -5V (V_{gs}), ($I_d=10mA$). The spectrum analyzer showed an oscillation at 9.33GHz, (see figure 7). From this measurement alone, it is indeterminate whether or not the oscillator is locked to the superconducting ring. To test for lock, with the oscillator still in the cryostat, its output was connected to a network analyzer. [9]

OSCILLATION FROM REACTION TYPE OSCILLATOR

Figure 7.

A one port measurement with the oscillator turned off, (DC voltages set to zero) showed a large return loss at 9.33GHz. This large return loss, "suck out", at the ring's resonant frequency, indicates a high probability that the oscillator is locked to the superconducting ring. The "suck out" disappears when the resonator's temperature is brought above its transition temperature. An additional test, turning the oscillator on and continuing to measure return loss, should show a reflection coefficient much greater than unity at the ring's resonant frequency. Setting V_{gs} and V_{ds} to -0.5V and 2.0V, respectively produced a large reflection coefficient much greater than unity at 9.33GHz and therefore provides additional verification that the oscillator is locked to the superconducting ring.

PARALLEL FEEDBACK OSCILLATOR

The parallel feedback oscillator consists of three distinct parts, a superconducting resonator, a high gain amplifier, and a 3dB splitter. This oscillator works by feeding part of the output signal back to the input of the amplifier, through the superconducting resonator. The resonator acts as a very narrow band pass filter whose pass band decreases as the Q - quality factor of the ring increases. If the feedback signal is in phase with the input signal, a phase shift

of 2π around the feedback loop, the amplifier will oscillate. [10]

The parallel feedback oscillator was built with the double sided thalium HTSC half wavelength resonator. For this test, the resonator was cooled to cryogenic temperatures, while the amplifier and the 3dB power splitter were kept at room temperature external to the cryogenic chamber. For oscillation to occur the loop gain has to be greater than one. An amplifier with gain greater than 22dB is required, since insertion loss around the loop totals approximately 22dB, 17dB of loss from the ring, 3dB splitter from the splitter, and approximately 2dB from the cables and connectors. An amplifier with 26dB of gain was used. Proper phase shift to provide for positive feedback around the loop, was provided by an appropriate length of semirigid coaxial cable. [10] A schematic of the oscillator configuration is shown in figure 8.

PARALLEL FEEDBACK OSCILLATOR

Figure 8.

Cooling the resonator to 46.7 K and turning on the amplifier produced an oscillation at 9.547GHz, which coincides with the resonant frequency of the ring at 46K, (see figure 9). The signal is extremely stable mainly due to the high quality factor of the double sided HTSC resonator.

PARALLEL FEEDBACK OSCILLATION

Figure 9.

A theoretical analysis of oscillator phase noise characteristics was made so that general trends and the effects of HTSC on oscillators could be understood. The relative numbers should only be viewed since phase noise is dependent on a large number of variables. For this analysis, the standard Leeson model was used. [11] The single sideband phase noise of a feedback oscillator is:

$$L(\omega) = 10 \log_{10} [N^2 (1 + \omega_0^2 / 4Q^2 \omega^2) (GFkT/P + \alpha/\omega)]$$

$L(\omega)$ =noise power relative to carrier

- N =frequency multiplication factor
- ω_0 =unmultiplied oscillator frequency
- ω =offset frequency in radian/s
- P =power output of amplifier
- G =loop gain of oscillator
- k =Boltzmann's constant
- T =absolute temperature
- α =empirically determined flicker-noise constant
- F =amplifier noise figure
- Q =unloaded quality factor of superconducting resonator

Present day superconducting resonators have Q's comparable to those of dielectric resonators. Commercially available dielectric resonators at X - band have Q's in the range of about 10,000 to 20,000. [12] A theoretical comparison, using the Leeson model, between two feedback oscillators, shows the oscillator which uses a resonator with a loaded Q = 19,000 has single sideband phase noise approximately 5db lower than the oscillator which uses a resonator with a Q = 10,000, given all other factors are the same, (see figure 10). Also shown is superconducting oscillator's phase noise as a function of temperature (see figure 11). The phase noise decreases as temperature decreases, since the Q of the resonator increases. This shows the great influence a resonator's quality factor can have on oscillator phase noise.

Theoretical Phase Noise Comparison of a 9.5 GHz Oscillator Using a Dielectric Resonator and a Double Sided HTS Resonator

Figure 10.

Theoretical SSB Phase Noise @ 1 KHz of HTS Stabilized 9.5 GHz Oscillator as a Function Of Decreasing Temperature and Increasing Quality Factor

Figure 11.

CONCLUSION

Implementation of HTSC oscillators is heavily dependent on the targeted systems. A distinct advantage of superconducting resonators over dielectric resonators is that superconducting resonators are planar and can be etched into the exact position each time to control coupling. A dielectric resonator oscillator requires the labor intensive task of positioning and securing the dielectric resonator for each oscillator built. For some systems the HTSC's need for cooling can overcome the HTSC advantages. Other systems such as certain ground systems and infrared systems which contain cryogenic cooling can take advantage of the low phase noise and other advantages that HTSC stabilized oscillators offer.

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